

MSPProfileR report

I. Data loading

- Number of spectra loaded: 676

II. Preprocessing

Trimming

Parameters

- Minimum mass: 2000 m/z
- Maximum mass: 20000 m/z

Results

Conformity test

Results

Criteria	Results
Number of empty spectra	0
Number of irregular spectra	0
Number of different lengths	0

Parameters

- Exclude empty spectra: Yes
- Exclude irregular spectra: Yes

Cleaning

Parameters

- Method used to transform intensity: Sqrt
- Method used to smooth intensity: Savitsky-Golay
- Half window size: 10
- Method used to remove baseline: SNIP
- Number of iterations: 100
- Method used to calibrate intensity: TIC

Results

Quality control

Parameters

- Scale estimator: Q
- Method used for the identification of atypical spectra: RC
- Threshold: 3
- Include lower spectra: Yes

Results

- Number of typical spectra: 656/676

- Number of atypical spectra: 20/676
- Atypical spectra: 89: Culex_dunni_TH_232 [F1], 90: Culex_dunni_TH_232 [F2], 92: Culex_dunni_TH_232 [F4], 123: Culex_dunni_TH_25 [G12], 365: Culex_portesi_TH_33 [B10], 366: Culex_portesi_TH_33 [B11], 367: Culex_portesi_TH_33 [B12], 387: Culex_portesi_TH_38 [C7], 606: Culex_usquatus_TH_78 [G6], 610: Culex_usquatus_TH_79 [G11], 611: Culex_usquatus_TH_79 [G12], 612: Culex_usquatus_TH_79 [G9], 617: Culex_usquatus_TH_81 [F10], 618: Culex_usquatus_TH_81 [F11], 619: Culex_usquatus_TH_81 [F12], 620: Culex_usquatus_TH_81 [F9], 623: Culex_usquatus_TH_82 [G3], 624: Culex_usquatus_TH_82 [G4], 638: Culex_usquatus_TH_86 [H6], 640: Culex_usquatus_TH_86 [H8]

Averaging

Parameters

- Method: Mean

Results

- Number of spectra before merging: 656
- Number of spectra after merging: 168

III. Processing

Peak detection

Parameters

- Noise estimator method: MAD
- Half window size:
- SNR: 3

Results

Average number of peaks for SNR 3: 104.44 (sd: 15.7)

Culex_adamesi_TH_2 [A5 A6 A7 A8]

Spectrum alignment

Parameters

- Method for reference peaks: MAD
- Minimum frequency of reference peaks: 0.5
- Tolerance for reference peaks: 0.002
- Warping method for alignment: Lowess

Results

- Number of reference peaks: 30

19336.4 m/z
18254.8 m/z
17173.2 m/z
16091.6 m/z
15010 m/z
13928.4 m/z
12846.8 m/z
11765.2 m/z
10683.6 m/z
9602 m/z
8520.4 m/z
7438.8 m/z
6357.1 m/z
5275.5 m/z
4193.9 m/z
3112.3 m/z
2030.7 m/z

Peak binning

Parameters

- Method for binning: Strict
- Tolerance for reference binning: 0.002

Results

Number of peaks: 773

Peak filtering

Parameters

- Minimum frequency: 0.2

Results

Number of peaks: 194

Intensity matrix

Parameters

- Fill missing intensities using the aligned spectra: Yes

Results

IV. Annotations

Names	Values
Number of annotations	169
Number of spectra	169
Number of annotation without spectrum	0
Number of spectra without annotation	0